

RESEARCH PAPER

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The odyssey of Gigolos in southern Philippines: Perks and drawbacks

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Key words: Prostitution, Gigolos, Perks, Drawbacks

<http://dx.doi.org/10.12692/ijb/26.1.88-106>

Article published on January 05, 2025

Abstract

The study delved into the life stories of gigolos in the twin cities of Southern Philippines. The study sought answers on the experiences of the informants as gigolos, the causes that drive the informants to engage in their job, and the impact of the informants' job to their lives. Transcendental phenomenological approach was used in the study. The study utilized ten (10) research informants who were known and identified as gigolos. It was conducted in the southern part of the Philippines specifically in the twin cities of Zamboanga del Norte. The researcher utilized interview guides in the conduct of individual personal in-depth interview. Thematic content analysis was used in the treatment of collected data. The researcher generated three (3) themes for the experiences of the informants as a gigolo, namely: Performance-Based Incentives, Gratuities, and Downfalls of Services. As to the causes that drive the informants to engage in their job, the latter formulated three (3) themes, namely: Money Dictates, Educational Pursuit, and Bounty Hunter. On the impact of the informants' job to their lives, three themes were created: Shameful Defeat, Health Glitch, and Parental Restraint. It was recommended that the government must uplift the poverty rate of the people. Creation of organization tasked in monitoring and tracking down known gigolos. Penalized any forms of male prostitution including their clientele. Awareness campaign on the adverse effects of becoming a gigolo, how this affects them, their families, friends, studies, the community, and its health related risk. Lastly, family and communities acceptance on their reintegration in to the community.

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Introduction

One of the oldest occupations was prostitution, which was once seen as a sin. The customer and the prostitute must trade financial benefits and sexual pleasures in order to perform this profession. Although guys and transgender people make up a significant portion of prostitutes in many places, scholars have traditionally concentrated on female prostitution while ignoring male and transgender prostitution (Weitzer, 2011; Weitzer, 2005). Male prostitutes who serve clients are referred to as "gigolos." The male and female prostitutes were not very different from one another; sex trade transactions are typically carried out in secrecy and under the "shadow of the night." To conceal their status, gigolos often work as students. Resto-bars, KTV lounges, and other nightclubs where male street prostitutes frequently offer themselves to potential clients driving by are among the places where they openly conduct business.

Call boys and escorts have social skills that enable them to relate to well-educated, upper-class clientele, and they may form emotional bonds with some of their frequent clients, according to Smith *et al.* (2009), as referenced by Weitzer (2011). As with all forms of prostitution, there are hazards and issues associated with male prostitution. The most harmful effects of these unethical behaviors were related to health, specifically the risk of contracting and spreading sexually transmitted infections (STIs, HIV, and AIDS). According to Baral *et al.* (2015), male gigolos, also known as male sex workers (MSWs), are more susceptible to contracting HIV on several levels. High numbers of sexual partners, extensive and intricate sexual networks, effective HIV transmission during unprotected anal contact, and intensified intersectional stigmas are all contributing factors. Furthermore, Baral *et al.* (2015) observed that, despite the global HIV epidemic being on the decline, there was increasing evidence of a persistent or increasing HIV burden among certain marginalized women. HIV acquisition and transmission among MSW were being amplified by

a number of synergistic facilitators, including structural, behavioral, and biological factors.

The stigma and criminalization of HIV, commercial sex, and same-sex behaviors raise MSWs' risk of infection and make it harder for them to get necessary services. Male prostitution posed health concerns, but it also carried legal and criminal dangers, physical abuse, rejection by friends and family, social shame, gay-bashing, economic risks due to unreliable revenues, and mental and emotional risks. It has been shown that adolescents and fugitives engaged in sex work are vulnerable. This type of behavior was prevalent in the town where the researcher hails from, and it moved the researcher to see these gigolos performing sexual favors for cash at such a young age. It piqued his curiosity to find out why they were engaging in these kinds of activities.

Materials and methods

This study utilized the transcendental phenomenological approach developed by Edmund Husserl. Which introduced the 'life-world' experiences or 'lived experience' and claimed that mind aimed at objects and used the term 'intentionality' to define his claim (El-Sherif, 2017). This method was used to explore the lived experiences and challenges of the male gigolos in the different cities of Southern Philippines. This design was employed because the study used non-numerical data to interpret and analyze people's experiences and actions. The goal of the study was to get the informants' perspectives and expressed views from the points of view of their own words, beliefs, and structures. An open-ended gathering of data and conversational communication were employed in this study through individual personal interviews with the informants.

The study took place in the northern part of the Zamboanga peninsula, which was located in Region IX in the northwestern part of Mindanao. The Zamboanga peninsula was a long semicircular peninsula extending toward the southwestern part of

the Sulu Archipelago and Borneo. The location was comprised of a total land area of 1,690,403 hectares, with a total population of 3,629,783 which was comprised of 67 municipalities and five cities (Sarmiento, n.d.).

The study focused on the province of Zamboanga del Norte, which has a total area of 7,301.00 square kilometers (2,818.93 sq mi) it occupies the northern Zamboanga Peninsula in western Mindanao. The Sulu Sea borders the province to the north and west, Misamis Occidental to the northeast, and Zamboanga del Sur and Zamboanga Sibugay to the south. The location of the study was further delimited in the City of Dapitan and Dipolog, where the rampant proliferation of male prostitution and male gigolos are taking place. Thus, they were chosen as the informants who provided the best information regarding the study.

Qualitative research needed only a smaller sample compared to the quantitative analysis; thus, in this research, the researcher looked for ten (10) research informants who were known and identified as male gigolos or male prostitute from the twin cities of Zamboanga del Norte. They underwent individual in-depth interviews. Informants are known and identified male gigolos, and they were chosen and categorized based on the typology of work, health condition, factors influencing them to engage in such activities.

The researcher utilized interview guides for the ten (10) informants in the individual personal interview of selected male gigolos in Dapitan and Dipolog City. In the study, phenomenological interviews were used to determine reciprocity in data collection to describe the meaning of concept or phenomenon in male prostitution, experiences, challenges, and mechanisms related to their work.

During in-depth interviews, interview guides containing open-ended questions were used by the researcher. The researcher asked questions while taking down notes to write down their responses. The

dialogs were also audio taped, taped with the informants' permission, which was later transcribed by the researcher.

The instrument was first validated by the panel to measure what the research study supposed to measure. The research instrument was made up of three parts. The first part concentrated on informants' experiences as male gigolos; the second part questions about the causes that drive the informants to engage in their jobs; the last part was about the impacts of the informants' job to their lives.

The thematic code analysis was employed to inspect themes which were transpired during the analysis of interview responses to measure the frequency of issues and similarities between the informants' use of themes. The thematic code analysis of Braun and Clarke (2006) was employed in this research. This method has six (6) steps as follows: (1) familiarization of data allowing the researcher to actively engage in the data by first transcribing the conversations in the individual in-depth interview, and then followed by reading the transcript or listening to the recordings and ideas written down; (2) generating initial codes for features of data that appeared exciting and meaningful; (3) searching for themes, which was the start of the interpretive analysis of the collated codes which was relevant data that were extracted and sorted according to overarching themes and the researcher's idea should allude connection among codes, subthemes, and themes; (4) reviewing themes means that the researcher needed to question whether to merge, refine, isolate or delete thematic initials; (5) defining and naming themes involves refining and defining the themes and potential subthemes within the data, and ongoing analysis was required to enhance the identified themes further and provide theme names concisely and effectually; and (6) producing the report was the final output of the study in which the researcher transformed his / her presentation into an interpretable piece of writing through the used of vivid and convincing extracts relating to subjects, study questions, and literature.

Results and discussion

This chapter presents the findings from the interview using a concise Husserlian–phenomenological approach with the seven (7) steps of Colaizzi's data analysis to provide an informative evaluation of the study.

To explicitly connect the coverage of the study, each informant was allowed to speak the mother tongue to express their experiences verbally. For general readability and comprehension, these have been translated. Likewise, all the statements from the informants were selected from the transcribed interview. Out of each significant account extracted, formulated meanings were created and coded as it reflected a comprehensive description of the informant's experience. The core concepts formulated that appeared to a specific category and representing particular structures were grouped into cluster themes. Lastly, cluster themes were then re-grouped to come up with the emergent themes.

After the thorough and profound description of the formulated meanings using Colaizzi's data analysis method as adapted by Abalos *et al.* (2016), fifteen (15) cluster themes were identified and re-grouped to form nine (9) emergent themes. They are the following:

I. Experiences of the informants

1. Performance-based incentives
2. Gratuities
3. Downfalls of services

II. Causes that drive the informants to engage in their job

1. Money Dictates
2. Educational Pursuit
3. Bounty Hunter

III. Impact of the informants' job to their lives

1. Shameful Defeat
2. Health Glitch
3. Parental Restraint

The experiences of the informants as gigolo revealed underneath the presentations and explanations of emergent themes.

I. Experiences of the informants as gigolo

Exploring the experiences of the gigolos firsthand was a great journey. It was new to the informant, telling the things they been keeping in secrets. As the researcher go along and establish confidence in them, the latter have gained their interest and started narrating openly about their work. He then generated three (3) emergent themes that were focused on the experiences of the informants. The following themes are:

1. Performance-based incentives

The first theme depicts the nature of their job. Working as a gigolo is not an easy job; they need to establish communication first with their clients. Most of the clients were from the referral of a friend. After establishing contacts, the client and the gigolo then agree on the price and the acts that they will do. Most likely, they will meet up somewhere secretive and away from the eyes of the public. Based on the accounts of Informant 3, he said that:

Ana jud sir... Sa barkada-- gikan sa barkada..mga contact sa barkada.. nakajamming napod nimo.. nakasuod-suod.. ingon ato na dayun.. mu offer-offer nga ingon ana... Contact ra sa cellphone sir dayun muingon sila nga adtu sa ilang balay unya ingon aning orasaha..mga gabie na dapit.. mga kadlawon usahay sa mga pension house.. ingon ana sir (ID13:SS1).

(That's it, Sir. From my friends or contacts of my friends. Getting together, making friends, just like that. Offering services. Communicating through cellphones, then they will invite you to visit their house at a certain time, night time, or at dawn in lodging houses. Just like that, Sir).

In this type of job, the informant may have met different kinds of clients. Their identity will always be kept confidential. This is to protect not only the identity of the gigolo and the clients but also their reputation. Informant 1 clearly stated that:

Naa man poy..mga professional man pod ang uban mao nang sa layu, maabot mig layu didto namu kuanon. Naay mga kuan sir uy., mga politician, mga ingon ana naay kuan lang.. katong mga teacher naa juy mga ingon ana gyud, naay mga nurse ingon ana nga trabaho ba.. klasi-klasi lang sir uy. Kanang uban sir mga balu, mangkay, nga katong mga sekreto ra sir ba..pero naay mga trabaho, kasagaran naay uban pod ana naa sa gobyerno gatrabaho, naa poy uban nga pari-pariha rapod pero naa lang gyud silay kwarta, mga OFW ingon ana, dayun wala nay mga bana sir ba, ang uban bulag ang uban balu. Di paka ana... makatira naka (IDI1:SS3).

(Some professionals wanted to do the act away from their place. There are also politicians, teachers, nurses and those different professions. Some are widowed, unmarried, those who are secretive, Sir. They have jobs, some even work in the government, and some are OFWs who have been separated or widowed).

The job requires clientele sexual satisfaction for the gigolo to be compensated. The payment of the services given was based on the level of sexual satisfaction the client receives. There were also limitations set and parts that were not included in the services. Performance should be equal to the payment. Informant 1 said that:

Mu serbisyo gyud me ana sir. Muromansa, mga lips to lips ingon ana naa poy mga parts nga wla napoy labot, depende man gud na sir mao nang ingon ana. Hatag ko 250, ahw! cge 250 walay labot hikap sa kuan.. akua. Mu ana man gud pod me, naa poy uban nga..basta sa bayot gyud sir kana gyud moy kuan kaayu nga... kanang.. muhatag sila palangnitan dosmil.. ang performance nimo ana kinahanglan kantidad pod ug dosmil kay malugi pod na sila syempre ikaw dosmil gud pod na, kwarta na gud na di paka musugot. Ah! Bahala na ni (IDI1:SS4).

(We give services, Sir. From romance, kissing just like that, some parts are not included, depending on the amount given. I will give 250, okay, but you cannot

touch some parts. For example, they will provide two thousand, and you will match that with a performance worthy of the money they give to be fair with them. So, who are you to deny that two thousand? Yes! Let's do it).

Every sexual act also comes with different prices. It comes with various actions, simple acts, complicated acts, and even comes in bundles or packages. Informant 3 specified that:

Tagaan kag kwarta sir..kwarta ra gyud.. usahay 1500 ingon ana 1000.. depende sir ug unsa kanang... naa mani silay kuan-kuan nga all-out daw. all-out tanan na gyud daw.. dala na daw na unsa na luboton, dayun um-umon, dayun makighalok pod daw ka... Depende sa performance ug unsa kaayu inyong buhaton, maopoy ilang ihatag..ug halok-halok ra gamay ra kaayu (IDI3:SS2).

(They will give you money, money only. Sometimes they give 1000 depending on your performance. If it's all-out, it includes anal sex, blowjob, and kissing. The money they give depends on the performance you give).

2. Gratuities

The second theme showed the positive experiences of the gigolo in doing the job. This experience gave happiness and satisfaction to the gigolo while doing his job. Informant 2 proudly stated that:

Dako kaayug katabang sir uy..kanang pang allowance sa eskwelahan. daghan mga.. ug unsa imong mga panginahanglanon pamalitan man pod ka nila ug kanang mga beste nimo., t-shirt. dayun kanang motor gani naku karon sir, nabayad.. nakaapil gani sila ug bayad-bayad.. kahuoy sa Diyos naimpas ra gyud. bayaran rapod, dili rapod ingon nga kada bulan gyud, tagaan rapod ka usahay ba ug kuan kanang maapekhan na gyud kaayu ug way ibayad, tagaan rapod kag pambayad (IDI2:SS5).

(It is really of great help. For my allowance in school, the things I needed, they will also provide you with clothes,

t-shirt. She even paid part of the monthly amortization of my motorcycle. Thank God it is fully paid now. She will pay for it but not consecutively, just for the time when it's badly needed).

Aside from financial and material things received from the clients, the gigolo also received friendly advice and emotional support. Informant 3 stated that:

Tagaan kog kuan sadinha sir cellphone sir..Matingala lage ang uyab nganong nakacellphone. Kanang..kung tambag-tambag bya pud sir naa bya pud kay madawat nga tambag-tambag gekan nila maayu pud mutamabag mga inana sir.. Financial raman sir (IDI3:SS4).

(They give me cellphone, Sir. My girlfriend wonder where it came from. They also give advice, and they are right on that matter. Mostly financial Sir).

Moreover, in some instances comfort is given to the informant, and they were there whenever they need someone to talk to. In times of sadness and pain, a shoulder to lean on. Informant 4 emotionally reiterated that:

Aww..ug kuan sir..kaning..murag..ako mag away-away mis..akong..naa man gyud koy uyab nga batan on pareha nakog edad.. Usahay mag away mi sa akong uyab malipay rapud ko kay naa koy katawag laen nga makaistorya nako sya istoryahanay ming duha. O, makacomfort sa akoo..naa sya sa panahon nga kuan nga sakitan ko (IDI4:SS5).

(It's somewhat like were getting an argument. I really have a girlfriend of my age and sometimes when we argue with each other, I'm happy that I have another someone to talk to, the one that can comfort me whenever I'm in pain).

It has also helped in upgrading the fashion style of the gigolos. The way they dressed-up, the fragrance they wore and choosing their fashion line. Informant 10 mentioned that:

Nausob sir kay..sauna kay yagit man kaayu ko sauna kay wala man koy in ane nga mga sinina..dayun dili kaau ko kabalo ma—mamorma.. Maggisi-gisi man gale ta mieskwela gale ta ani..mga sapatos buslot pa..apike kayo..dako kaayu syag katabang nako..kaning trabahoa sir..kay..halos tanan nakong gamit..branded ang uban. Dayun naa pakay lami kayo nga bag nga suoton..lami kaayong sapatos..socks..dayun perfume..naa pay perfume!

(IDI10:SS13). (My life have changed Sir, because before I dressed-up like trash, and I don't know how to groom myself. I even go to school wearing shoes with holes on it, and worn-out shirts. This job really helps me a lot, because it affords me garments some even are branded. You will have a nice wear, good shoes and socks, and perfume).

3. Downfalls of services

This theme delved into the negative experiences of the gigolos that have caused them stress, unhappiness, and dissatisfaction with their job. Mutual agreement before doing the job is a must in order to establish the amount of money to be received and the type of sexual activities the gigolo needed to do. Informant 1 thoughtfully stated that:

Kanang kuan sir..na man guy usahay nga dili magsabot daan sa presyo ba. Dayun to mahitabo na, magromansaanay na..ingon ana syempre ingon ana man gyud na sila. Kay bayot gud muromansa gyud na silag laki then ikaw pod nga laki balos nalang pod ka kay bayran man ka. Dayun pagkahuman sir di na magkasinabot sa presyo ba, kanang ingon ana kay..buang ka..! humana ko nimu dayun dili ka muhatag ug kuan. Naa man poy mga bayot nga ingon ana sir, syempre kami nga mga laki dili pod me gusto nga magansi pod me sa among performance (IDI1:SS8).

(Sometimes Sir we cannot deal with the price. And then we do it, we do romance, they are like that. They are gays that's why they wanted to do romance with a man, and since you are a man you do it also in exchange of money. Then after that you cannot agree

on the price, just like that “You bullshit! After we had sex you will not give on what we agreed on.” There are also gays like that, and since we are men we cannot allow an unjust match to our performance).

Doing this job is indeed a struggle on the part of the gigolo. However, indeed these negative experiences happen sometimes. Moving on and just laughing on what had happened is their way of saying that “there were always ups and downs, being tricked is one of it.” Informant 7 added that:

Ako na tablahan ko kadaghan na kadaghan na usa ka buthanan tag 100 pa to 100 muna muna pato 17 di jud nako makalimtan yati gitablahan ko.. Pero gipainom ko niya tanduay duha ka senior pisti natingla man kong sigig inom hala gigamit ko niya bali niyang ugom chinupa sa akoo.. Matay tingala man ko giingnaman man kog mangihi sa ko dayon wala na hing balik (IDI7:SS12).

(Yes, for how many times I was not paid, 1 hundred for one load I’m just 17 years old at that time. I really can’t forget that experience. But he provided me a drink, that’s Tanduay 2 senior bottles, he did use me and do blowjob in me. I was surprised that he ask permission to urinate but did not come back to pay).

There were also instances that the clients paid only partial payment and the remaining payment to be paid on the next time they see each other. Informant 9 regretfully elaborated that:

Wala pod ko ka experience ana pero naka experience naku anang kulang iyang hatag..utang.. Giutang ang gamay ang kulang sunod na kita kay ikuan daw niya..ehh..daghang pasumangil sir.. daot kaayu sugot nalang pod ko kay gasolina lage daw (IDI9:SS8).

(I did not experience not being paid, what I experience is that the payment is lacking. The remaining balance will be paid next time we meet again. He got many alibis, that’s why I accepted it because according to him the remaining money is only for gasoline).

Gigolos work solely to earn money, but sometimes they experienced unjust treatment from their clients. They even experienced to be paid with just iced water, liquor, and cigarettes. Informant 10, while smiling, stated that:

Hah!..kana!..hah..tablahan ko ana sir..tulo tu kabuok bayot sir..atong ice water ug sigarilyo ray gihatag..gi..agi man gu anag..kuan gud way panigarilyo pud..ah gitagaan kog sigarilyo sir. Dayun uban atong kuan gyud gitablahan jud ko..igo ra gipainom sir dayun gigamit na dayun ko sir (IDI10:SS14).

(I have already experienced being unpaid for my services Sir. There were three gays at that time Sir and they just only paid me with an iced water and cigarettes. Others have only given me liquor in exchange of my services).

Unpaid services inevitably caused unhappiness since the job involves financial gain. However, aside from this, harassment and unpaid services cause more stress and unsatisfied feelings. Informant 10 tearfully shared that:

Dayun katong dakog lawas sir katung nitabla nako sir..nah!. Paghuman nakog ana sa akoo sir..ingon ramag kalit nga..oh dayun? Kay humana naman ta wala man koy kwarta magsinumbagay nalang ta ani ron..nah! Wala nalang pud ko nikuan sir..wala nalang ko nikuan kay dakog kaayug lawas sir uy..dako kaayu sir (IDI10:SS15).

(And there’s this one muscular guy who did not pay me for my services. After having sex with me, he just said “And now that we’re done and I don’t have money to pay we will just settle it with a fight?” I really don’t have a choice because he is so big and muscular, so, I didn’t do something about it).

II. Causes that drive the Informants to engage in their job

Every action has its very reason, and this part discusses the causes of why people engage and

continue engaging in becoming a gigolo. Many factors need to consider in explaining why people do such jobs. These three (3) themes explain the reasons why people engage and choose to continue the job.

1. Money dictates

Money is the very reason why people become a gigolo. This theme explains the contribution of money in influencing the will of every gigolo in doing the job. Informant 1 emphasized the importance of money why he does the job, and he stated that:

Number 1 jud sir kanang kwarta gyud. Kwarta gyud sir. Para..naa gyud kay mabunot ba. Naay kwarta gyud mabutang sa bulsa. Ah! Murag lisod sir. Dli. Wala. Kay ang kana gud amuang mu kuan me ana, mamayot me pangwarta raman gyud among gihunahuna (IDI1:SS13).

(Number 1 Sir is money. Money Sir, so that I have something to use. I have money on my pocket. It is difficult Sir. Because we engage into becoming a gigolo just for the money).

Informant 4 also supported the statement of Informant 1 about the influence of money in doing the job most notably that the informant still studying, he said that:

Kwar..kwarta pero pirmiro jud sir kana gyung kuan pinansyal gyud kwarta gyud labi na kay gaskwela ko karon sa allowance. Allowance nako unsa kayo akong ganahan diha..pali-palit kay igo-igo ragyud pud akong allowance nga gihatag sa akong pamilya dayun kuan pud kanang ipadayon nako ni sya kay ganahan man gyud ko sa iyaha gyud mao nang.. Ohhh..mao nang na develop nako niya gamay..pero naa man gyud koy uyab gyud (IDI4:SS10).

(Money, but it all started from financial reason Sir, most notably that I'm still studying for my allowance. For my allowance, for me to buy what I want to buy because the allowance that my family is giving just enough for my basic needs. That's why I'm still doing

this, and I'm now attracted to her. Yes, I'm a little bit attracted to her, but again, I have a girlfriend).

Becoming a gigolo is also the most natural way of earning money. Aside from working hard under pressure and the heat of the sun, being a gigolo requires only minimal use of strength and but comes with more compensation. Informant 6 specified and stated that:

Ahhh, mas dali ang kwarta sir, yes sir, kaysa sa sa,kining, trabaho tag ug sa binulan, sa mga sweldo sa part-rime, gagmay ramn, ay kining tag 200 ang adlaw ramn barato.. Maypay kining mamayot ka kay usa kalibong gabii, yes sir hmnn, lami pa sa feeling, kaysa mag, kaysa mag took kag imoa. Hhmn hmnn (IDI6:SS11).

(This is an easy money Sir compared to other jobs whose payment is monthly, part-time jobs are less paid at about 200 per day, and it's very cheap. I'd instead engage in becoming a gigolo because you're going to earn one thousand a night. Yes Sir, and I enjoy than masturbating).

Moreover, money sometimes dictates the gigolos do things beyond their limitations. What is important is money. Informant 7 elaborated his experiences and expressed that:

Lahi napod...Lahi ni sya nga bayot napod...Sos karon kay na...na encounter naman ko na lahi sya kay ang iyaha...na bangag sa akong lubot romansaon na tilapan na niya dayon iya ra kong mag lolo rako sya moy mu romance nako.. So murag kog gingilohan karon makig lips to lips sya nako so mura kog gingilohan karon makig lips to lips sya nako karon kay dili man ko kay kaning hugaw lage kayo pud kay lubot pud nako iyang gitilapan matay karon kay iya mang gikuan mudugang sya og dos mil kay kwarta kwartaan man pud sya so hing hatag sya napugos jud ko isig romansaay mi... Dili sa naa koy ika ulaw hing chupa pud ko duha jud mi romance jud ming duha...pulihanay balintuhanay pero wala nako lubuta niya (IDI7:SS3).

(It's the other gay, this gay is different from others that I've encountered. He licks and does erotic acts on my butt hole, I'll masturbate, and he'll do the romance. So, I really feel disgusted about it, and now he wanted to do kissing lips to lips; I refuse to do it, of course, that's dirty. And now he offers an additional 2 thousand for that erotic act, and then I'm pushed in doing it. I cannot deny or neither be shy to tell this, Sir, but I also do blowjob on him and do erotic acts also, but he decided not to do anal sex in me).

Apart from it, friends can also influence a person to engage in becoming a gigolo. Most especially when the people their calling friends are already a gigolo. However, then again, it will similarly fall into the reason for earning money and satisfying vices. Informant 10 on his account specified that:

Ag katong na..nag edad kog 16..kuyog-kuyog kos akong barkada..inom-inom mi..agi rapud atong..lage daw..kay so bata pa kay hangol man gud ug inom pa sir..asay jam tua. Dayun akong mga barkada mga mamayotay man sir...maotu sir..ila kong gituklod kay ingon daw sila sir lami man daw ng kuan sir..lami man daw sir (IDI10:SS10).

(At the time that my age was just 16 years old, I always go along with my friends, get drunk, and I'm always present at every party. My friends are also gigolos; that is why they influenced me to become a gigolo because it gives pleasure).

Gigolos even do the job to earn money to please their women. Gigolos are men and that cannot be denied that men are always attracted to women. Informant 1 further stated that:

Ahw! Kanang kuan sir..kanang naang mamayot me dayun para igasto pod sa babaye ba., para ibali pod didto. Oh, mamayot me daan dayun murag..ang kwarta sa bayot nga gikan namu mao pod toy igasto namu sa pagpamaye pod. Kay mas masatisfied man gyud me ug baye among magamit, mao nang mamayot me daan desir me mamaye, para naay igasto sa baye bah (IDI1:SS10).

(We engage into becoming a gigolo to provide for our women. Yes, we commit to becoming a gigolo for what we earn from the gays that will be provided to our women. It's because we are more satisfied when we have sex with women, that's why we go first to the gays before going to our women so that we can provide for them).

2. Educational pursuit

This theme also looked into the brighter side of why people chose to become a gigolo. Almost all of the informants are students, and earning money to fund their education is one of the main reasons why people engage in becoming gigolos. Informant 1 reiterated that:

Ang number 1 gyud sir kanang mga project sa eskwelahan mao nang gipursigi gyud me nga musulod nalang gyud ana. Sa., para sa tarong man pod nga pamaagi namu gigamit sir. Oh sir. Mga project, mga allowance diha na namu na gikuha (IDI1:SS6).

(The number 1 reason Sir are school projects; that's why we engage in those activities. We do that for a good cause. Yes, Sir. Projects, allowances came from that).

Their will to finish their studies motivated them to continue the job despite the danger it delivers. The money they earn from their work as a gigolo was used to fund school requirements, projects, and other expenses for school. It will also lessen the expenses of the parents, and the funding intended for him will be utilized for the different needs of the family. Informant 8 stressed that:

Dayon kanang, pag kanang sa pag eskwela, project, dili naku sa akong ginikanan mangayo palit ug project, kay didtu rako niya mangayu, mga gamit, karsones, sinina, kana sir (IDI8:SS14).

(Also, for my studies, for my projects, I will not ask any more from my parents in buying projects, I will ask from the gay. He also provides me garments, pants, that's it, sir).

Sometimes the lack of support from the parents for sustaining their education has pushed them to do the job. Furthermore, because money was scarce, they find their ways to address the problem by engaging in this kind of activity. Informant 10 on his accounts said that:

Kani nisulod pud ko ani sir kay..para sa pagskwela sir..kay..akong mama kay dili man—dili man kasuporta sa akong sir (IDI10:SS11).

(I entered this job because of my studies because my parents cannot afford to support me).

Poverty is one of the hindrances in the life of the gigolo in achieving their dreams. And since getting a degree and finishing studies is their number one priority, they need to prioritize first addressing the problem of the scarcity of money to achieve these goals. It was emphasized on the statement of Informant 10, and he stated that:

Para sir sa..makahuman ug eskwela sir mao ragyud na sir..makahuman kog eskwela. Naa rapuy mugasto nako sir..kining nagpadayun kog in ane sir para pud..sa ako pong uyab sir.. Para naa pud koy magasto sir..di lisod bya pud mi sir..di jud mi datu sir..pobre bya mi sir..di..padayun ko ani sir..kay..para lang makasuroy-suroy pud ko sa akong uyab..mahatag pud nako sir..di mao nang gami-maintain ko anang bayot gyud (IDI10:SS12).

(For me to finish my studies, Sir, someone who can support me. I continue doing this for me to have money for my girlfriend. So that I can afford to buy something I want. We are very poor, that's why I remain doing it, for me to have money and for me to treat my girlfriend for a date).

3. Bounty hunter

The theme looked at gigolo's material desires and needs, which are also one of the reasons for doing the job. Aside from the financial gains that a gigolo gets, they are also offered with personal belongings and personal material, which motivated them more on

continuing the job. Moreover, they can also buy things which were not given by their parents or family and even provided financial and material advantages to others. Informant 3 stated that:

Makapalit ka sa imong..ang..ganahan nimong paliton sir..like sa..mga panginanghalon sa skwelahan.. palit kag school shoes mga in ana sir..dayun naa kay paliton..palit kag mga sanina.. dayun imong pamilya matagaan nimog kwarta matingala imong..imong..akong igsoon nga in ana nga tagaan nimog kwarta..aha man ka gikan ug kwarta (IDI3:SS13)?

(You can buy whatever you want to buy Sir. Your needs in school, you can buy school shoes, just like that Sir. You can buy clothes, you can also share money to your family, and my sister wonder when I gave her money and ask if where it came from).

The advantages they get have even made their lives more comfortable and more accessible. They feel more confident and proud of owning things because their clients have funded them. Informant 4 confidently stated that:

Dako kaayog epekto sir murag kana lage sir murag naa koy kibali ug wala sya siguro murag di dagway ko maka motor. Siguro sir kay nitabang man gud pud syag makama makamotor pero mag lisod kog bayad siguro.. Kanang naa sya ron komportable kayo ko sa akong kinabuhi murag kursonada kayo ko kay kani mabayran ra gyud ni (IDI4:SS14).

(There is really a big effect Sir. Because without her, I cannot buy a motorcycle.Maybe Sir, because she helps me but it will be difficult for me to pay for it. Now that she's here, I'm confident that this will be paid).

Besides, it also gives economic independence on the part of the gigolo since they do not ask any more money from his parents every time they need money. Their parents no longer provided money for them since they have received money from their clients. Aside from economic independence, they also gained

economic stability because sometimes support from gays was given every month. Informant 6 stated that:

ahhhh. Epekto sa akong kinabuhi sir is, dili na kayu, dili na kayu mag gastu akong ginikanan sa akua, kay naa naman koy , pinadal-an man ko, pinadal-an man ko sinimana, dina kaayu makaapeke, dili ra kayu sila maggastu sa akua, daun ,ahhh ahh ,hmmnn, murag mao to sir, daun silbi independent, in ana. Yes sir (IDI6:SS13).

(The effects in my life Sir is that they will not be spending money on me, because I am receiving weekly from my patrons. I am not in need anymore, they will not anymore spend money on me. That's all Sir, I'm now independent. Yes Sir).

Acquiring material equipment and providing needs for the family, which gives comfort on their way of living, was one of the pulling factors of the job in becoming a gigolo. Buying material belongings and paying for some monthly amortizations attracts people to continue the job. Informant 7 further discussed and stated that:

Ang maayong epekto is nakatigom kog gamit para sa akong mga pamilya dayon motor hapit na maimpas agi rapud nila monthly na straight monthly nako ana wa kuan gud sir kana akoang motor monthly 1700 dala rebates dos mil aww sos usa ra kabuthanan sa bayot na sir dali ra kaayo (IDI7:SS21).

(The good effect is that I earned properties for my family and then my motorcycle is almost fully paid because of being a gigolo. The monthly amortization for my motorcycle is just 1 thousand 7 hundred together with the rebates 2 thousand, that's just one full session with a gay. That's very easy).

III. Impact of the informants' job to their lives

This part explained the different effects of the informants' job on their lives. These experiences were either negative or positive experiences that have made a significant change in their way of living.

1. Shameful defeat

The job of being a gigolo always emanated with stigma, and the public is not amenable to this kind of job, thus enticing other people to humiliate people doing this job. This theme showed the different embarrassing moments that the gigolo experienced in doing the job. Moreover, it affects the lives of every gigolo negatively. Informant 1 elaborated the experiences that have given him so much embarrassment, and he said that:

Number 1 sir kana naang..kana lage nga malibak naka kay ilado na kaayu ka nga ing ana ka.. nindot. Maot na kaayu kag kuan sir ba kana naang background nimo. Pero sa imo ra pong amigo nga nakaila nimo. Mao to sila ug mutsismis to sila..mu.. makalat jud.. ug ilaang e kuan (IDI1:SS14).

(Number 1 Sir is that you are being chattered and known to be like that. You will have a bad background, especially to those who know you. They will surely spread the rumors).

Bullying from their friends and the people around them was also the adverse effects of doing the job. It has given worry on the part of the gigolo that their identity may be known to the public and their family. Informant 3 stressed about this issue on his accounts and stated that:

Bahin sa akong trabaho sir? Kanang maulaw ka sir kay surahon ka nila ana..Mailado ka kay ana kay ipanabi in ana. Maabot sa imong ginikanan palang nga in ana ka.. Wala raman pud sir kay dili raman pud mutuo kay ako raman pung ingnon nga wala (IDI3:SS5).

(About my job Sir? You will be bullied Sir, you will be identified as such. Your parents might know about it, but they don't believe it).

Being bullied sometimes resulted in arguments and trouble because of defending themselves to retract the chatters of the people. In the eyes of the people, doing this kind of job created a gap between them

because they feel disgusted on them in doing the job. Informant 3 again from his accounts stated that:

Kanang..sige kag sura-surahon nga in ana nga ing ana lage sir nga mamayot ko sir makakita nakag away kay.. Kay imo gyung idefend imong kaugalingon nga dili jud ka ing ana. Kanang mag away pod mo sa imong uyab. Mag argue mi pero naa moy argue-argue kay agi sa ing ana lage mamayot ka pero muingon gyud kag dili diay tinuod (IDI3:SS7).

(You will always be bullied Sir as gigolo to the point that you will get involve in a fight. Because you will defend yourself that you're not like that. You will even argue with your girlfriend proving that you're not a gigolo).

One of the greatest fear that a gigolo has hidden was when they are identified as such. Moreover, the people around them have humiliated them because of the nature of their job. The job they have carried a stigma in society and denied public approval; people even sometimes see them as social plague. Informant 8 feel discouraged and expressed that:

Kanang wala ko nalipay sir, kanang mga trashtalk sa ubang tawo.. Ahhh,, muingun nalang na ka, oh bullyhon sila nga. hilom diha, mamayotay ka!, ana nga, hugaw kaayo ka, basin naa nakay aids, ayaw doul-doul namu ana sir (IDI8:SS5).

(I'm not happy Sir because of the bullying I've received from other people. They will just tell me "shut-up, you're a gigolo," and that I'm very dirty, that I may have AIDS, don't go nearer to us, that's it Sir).

Aside from this discouragement, gigolos were also denied and not accepted by their families. Doing the job has also affected the good reputation of their family in the society. It brought shame and dishonor to the family and the people close to them. Informant 8 further discussed these issues and mentioned that:

Kanang sa, sa ginikanan pod, dili sila ganahan gusto, dili pod sila gusto kanang tutol pod sila sa, dili sila kuan nimu nga mamayotay ka. Ana, limpyo kaayu ta pagkatao daun, ana mao ranang trabaho nimu. Oh kabalo... kay ana lagi sila sir nga, dili dili-dili daw sila gusto nga ing ana, kay kanang, tarung, tarung ba daw ko pagkatawo kay nag kuan kuan ko ana, kana ra pod sir (IDI8:SS6).

(My parents also Sir don't want my job, they cannot accept the fact that I am a gigolo. And that the image of my family if very clean, and you have that kind of job. Yes, they know and they really don't want it. They even say and ask if I am on my right mind because of what I'm doing).

Aside from that, having money from the clients in a manner that was easy for them to achieve has let them believed in a false reality that they are wealthy. They have then thought that the money they got has grown to the point that they will extravagantly spend it even in non-sense things. Informant 3 shared that:

Madaot imoang kuan image sa mga tawo..kanang..murag nagpafeel nako nga naasenso ka ing ana.. Murag i-take advantage nimo ang kwarta..murag asenso ka sir.. Pero pag abot pag uli diay sa inyuha wala ra diay..murag nagpaka aron ingnon (IDI3:SS16).

(It will destroy your credibility to the people, that you might feel that you have preferment over others. Then you take advantage of the money. But when you get home, its just nothing, you are just pretending).

2. Health glitch

This theme elucidated on the adverse health effects of the job into the lives of every gigolo. What was unique about the work of a gigolo was their ability to have sex with multiple partners. This uniqueness enabled them to be more prone to different types of sexually transmitted diseases. People are even afraid to go near them because of the possibility of transmission. Informant 9 disappointedly reported that:

Ang naka kuan lang daghan na kaayung kuan sir nahadlok naku ato, maong dili naku mulubot, pachup raku nakasulay naman pod ko anang sakit nga nasira bitaw sir... Na sakit gyud kaayu na sir abtan ug pila ka semana tu nga akong otin nga ga nana.. Pagkuan na naku pag abri na naku pagkabuntag..pagpangihhi naku sakit gyud kaayu murag bus-awon ba times 10 ang kasakit sa bus-awon sir.. Sakit kaayu e-ihhi then imong brief bitaw, mga tulo ka brief naku buslot gyud tanan gyud agi sa nana daot kaayu (IDI9:SS7).

(I'm really afraid of being infected with diseases, that's why I don't do anal sex anymore, just blowjob. I have also experienced being infected with gonorrhea and it's very painful and for how many weeks my penis excretes pus. I really can't urinate well Sir because of the pain, and my underwear got damage because of that).

Furthermore, sometimes, being transmitted with diseases exacerbated the embarrassment, which has lower down their confidence to seek help. Such instances have caused them to try out some conventional ways of treating such infections, without any promise of improvement. Informant 10 narrated his negative experiences and mentioned that:

Daotan nga experience ag kato jung nasira ko sir..katong gitayhopan akong luso sir..kaingon kos sakong kugalingon..nah!..di gyud diay lalim ning mag ing ane..in ane diay. Makakita tag bayot nga salbahis pud diay..naa pud salbahis nga bayot pud..mao tung nasira ko..iyot kog butong hinuon..gisugba ang butong (IDI10:SS16).

(The negative experience I had is when I got infected with gonorrhea. I did say to myself that, this job is really not that simple. Most especially when our gay clients are barbaric and naughty, that's why I got infected with diseases. I've even tried the traditional belief of having sex to a roasted young coconut as a cure for gonorrhea).

Sexually transmitted diseases have spread easily, most especially if it was done with multiple sex partners. Having no definite clients who were not infected with diseases have worsened the probability

of infection, most especially if it was done without any protection. Informant 3 elucidated that:

Magkasakit ka sir..dili ka..kanang..naa kay makuha sa bahin sa kuan..kadugayan nimong gamit-gamit kay laki-laki gud..naa kay makuha nga sakit..dis advantages sir (IDI3:SS15).

(You will get sick Sir because of having sex with multiple partners, that's the disadvantage with it Sir).

In the event of infection, gigolos have suffered the most difficult moments of their lives. Seeking help, finding a cure, and health status have been at stake. These instances have led to depression and to the point of seeking revenge and infecting it to other people. Informant 7 revengefully stated that:

Ahh sira jud ni soo mga unom pito ba ka bayot naka takod jud pud ko ako jud nang gi among nila, gigamit gamit nam gamit na karon nasira ko gigamit nako sya karong adlaw a abtag mga 3 days o 2 days pa lang daan hilak nag nana akong oten bali nakong puga unsaon na mani ngita kog palit ug tambal karon kay akong gibuhat gisugo nako akong bata gipasulat lang nako gihatag niya di man muhatag ug kuan tambal kay bata man so ako nalay nangursunada ako rang gilantaw sila ayy mog lantaw gisugo rako ani pero wala sila kabalo ako juy nadaot hmmm ayy mog kuan kay ako ray gisugo rako ani dili ko ingon ani ana rako ba (IDI7:SS14).

(I got infected with gonorrhea and after 2 to 3 days I already felt the symptoms and as a retaliation I did pass it to about 7 gays, before taking medicines to cure it. I wrote down the name of the medicine and instructed my child to buy me that medicine, but he was denied because he was just a child. I have no choice, so, I went to the pharmacy and looked at them saying that "I'm just being requested to buy it, I'm not like what you think").

3. Parental restraint

This theme portrayed the refusal of the parents or family members on the chosen job of the gigolo. It

was unacceptable on the part of the parents and family, knowing that their family members are gigolos. Family reputation was really at stake, and it has also attracted public humiliation. Informant 4 mentioned that:

Naa sir, kay kanang sa kuan kanang akong pamilya murag nakaatik na sila murag nasuko na akong pamilya sa akua murag.. O, akong magulang, akong magulang nakaatik na sya iya nakong ginabadlong kay paundangan na..kay kauban man pud silag kuan volleyball sa akong magulang (IDI4:SS6).

(I have Sir, it's because my family might have an idea about it and got angry with me. Yes Sir, my elder sister. She knows about it and reprimand me to stop it, because they are team mates in playing volleyball). The job has also instigated disputes among family members and has destroyed family ties.

Walking in the community with this stigma has also affected the family and the reputation they are protecting. Providing the needs and wants of the family from the fruit of this job have destroyed their dignity and may cause disappointment from their love ones. From the start of doing the job until retiring, the stigma has always be marked on them. Informant 7 narrated his experiences and stressed that:

Hapit pajud mi nag bulag atu sir kay agi atung iya nakong giprangkahan atong mga 5 months dagway iyang tiyan dayun natungnan pajud tu wala koy ika abang sa balay ana sya pero wala pa tu diser atu wala pa wala pa ko kitag kwarta na ehh iabang sa balay hing ana sya nga musugot raka taman mag ka dako imong bata mag ka tigul sa karon okay paka kay bata bata paman ka kung magka edad ka naa pa ba kahay mupatul nimo maoy iyahang istorya so murag naka sulod pud sa akong huna huna.. Pero sa na abtan ug times na nanginahanglan napud kog kwarta naa man koy kaduolang bayot so hing duol napud ko so nakabayad ko niya mao natuy higayon ni ana syag di gyud ka mag undang mag bulag nalang ta mang lakaw mi..soo hing uli silag bukid gidala nila ang

akohang bata. Karon kay ako gusto napud ko ma platar balik na hing ga nag pagamit gigamit napod nako ang bayot giapas napod nako sila dayon taman karon sir wala kahibalo akong asawa (IDI7:SS18).

(My wife almost broke-up with me and tell me frankly "Is it okay with you doing that job until our children grows up, you're not getting younger, you're getting older and not all the time you will have clients. Those were the times when she's still 5 months pregnant and that's very untimely because I don't have money to pay for the rent of our house. I am also thinking about what my wife was saying, but again I was test by time and I'm in need badly of money that's why I did it again. At that time my wife made a decision of leaving me while bringing my children with her. And now that I wanted to settle down with my family, but at first I was used again by that gay and after earning money I fetch my family to go home and until now my wife has no idea that I'm still operating as a gigolo).

Despite the evils brought by the job, some have continued doing it because they have no other choice of earning money. Doing the job of a gigolo provided financial advantages and sexual pleasure; these factors motivated the will of the gigolo not to stop the job. Informant 9 elaborated that:

Wala sir uy..! Mubabag gani akong ginikanan sir kay nakaingon nga known na daw kaayu ko nga mamayutay pero... Wala gyuy laing mahimo sir kay wala man pod silay kwarta apiki gyud pod lage..mao nang wala gyud koy laing mabuhat gyud, mao ragyud nang trabahua (IDI9:SS14).

(No Sir! Even my parents can't accept the fact that I'm a very known gigolo in our place, but they cannot do something about it because we don't have money and we're very poor. That's why I don't have a choice but to continue my job as a gigolo).

Aside from that, finishing their studies because their clients funded them was not an assurance of acceptance of the family or parents. Being a gigolo

was considered an immoral act that denied public approval and family acceptance. It has caused stigma and embarrassment, and the job also increased the possibility of spreading and transmission of diseases. Informant 7 enunciated that:

Akong gipa ila ila sa akong mama pag graduate nako karon kay kuan na gipa ila ila akong inahan dili kadawat kay nganong ingon ana daw bayot daw ana dayon maot daw kaayog nawong dako kaayo baboy ana.. Gi kuan sa akong mama dayon dili sya kadawat so akong gibuhat himpalit man sya og letson baboy kanang gamay gamay rapud mga 30 kilos gibilin namo nang lakaw mi (IDI7:SS8).

(I introduced him to my mother during my graduation, but my mother could not accept that my partner is a gay, very fat and ugly. My mother could not accept it, what I did since the gay bought roasted pig for my celebration we left it behind and we walk away).

Moreover, problems brought by becoming a gigolo caused an issue that may lead to a dispute between their parents and clients. The denial of acceptance of the parents of the job enabled them to find ways on how to control or stop it. These issues have resulted in fights or arguments between parents and clients. Informant 7 reiterated that:

Hmm..kato mga problema dayon naay usa jud na nahubog pud ang bayot gisulong akong mama kay kani laging silingan ra gud pud namo kani lageng ingon akong mama na si ako daw gi sigi daw kog gi kuan ba huthutan sigig gamiton daw ana dayun bisan dili na daw ba gapalabaw pud akong mama ba para unsa pud so gisulong sa bayot nahubog ahh hapit mag layog yati pud ning kinabuhia ni maotung na kuan nako (IDI7:SS16).

(Those problems, and then the other problem was when another client of mine got drunk and assail my mother because we're just neighbors and he have heard gossips that the gay was always using me eventhough it's not true. My mother has made false

information about the gay and me that's why she assailed and almost had a fight with that gay).

Conclusion

The magnificent nine (9) emergent themes were created after the data was thoroughly gathered from the informants. These themes were arranged as follows: *Performance-Based Incentives, Gratuities, Downfalls of Services, Money Dictates, Educational Pursuit, Bounty Hunter, Shameful Defeat, Health Glitch, and Parental Restraint.*

The researcher has generated three (3) themes for the experiences of the informants as a gigolo, namely: *Performance-Based Incentives, Gratuities, and Downfalls of Services.*

As to the causes that drive the informants to engage in their job, the latter formulated three (3) themes, namely: *Money Dictates, Educational Pursuit, and Bounty Hunter.*

On the impact of the informants' job to their lives, three themes were created: *Shameful Defeat, Health Glitch, and Parental Restraint.*

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